

**WHAT IS MORE EFFECTIVE? SINGLE CELEBRITY VERSES
MULTIPLE CELEBRITY: A STUDY ON RELATIVE EFFECTIVENESS
OF BOTH TYPE OF PRINT ADVERTISEMENTS ON CONSUMERS’
PERCEPTION**

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ABSTRACT

The Study is mainly done to find out the relative effectiveness of Single Celebrity endorsed Advertisement and multiple Celebrity endorsed Advertisement in influencing the perception of consumers (i.e. attitude towards advertisement, attitude towards celebrity and attitude towards advertised product). Further, the Study is done for the Same Product and for the low involvement Product especially Soft drinks.

Given the purpose of the study, the descriptive research technique is used. In the Study, Low-involvement Product Category is considered and two type of endorsed Advertisements (Single Celebrity and Multiple Celebrity) are used and the study is done on 200 Consumers. Created Print Advertisements are used as stimuli.

The study suggest that for low-involvement product category specifically Soft-drink especially in case of Print media, advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities has more favourable/positive impact in influencing the Perception of consumers (i.e. attitude towards advertisement, attitude towards celebrity and attitude towards advertised product) as compared to advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity.

Limitation of the study is that it is restricted/confined to the selected city of Gujarat and therefore the findings may or may not be generalized to the other cities or states of the country.

A major implication from the findings for the managers or advertising agencies is that as the number of celebrities increases in the advertisement, the impact of advertisement in creating positive attitude towards advertisement increases, also the consumer purchase intention for the advertised product and the consumer’s perception towards celebrity’s credibility, trustworthiness, attractiveness and expertise increases for the low-involvement Soft drink Product especially in case of Print media.

The contribution of the study is in addressing an area that has not been very well researched yet, and in addressing a research question that has not been investigated properly.

Keywords:

Single Celebrity, Multiple Celebrity, Perception of Consumers, Print Advertisements, attitude, Purchase Intention.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A celebrity endorser is “an individual who enjoys public recognition and who uses this recognition on behalf of a consumer good by appearing with it in an advertisement” (McCracken, 1989). Friedman and Friedman state that “a celebrity endorser is an individual who is known to the public for his or her achievement in areas others than of the product class endorsed” (Friedman & Friedman, 1979).

Celebrity Endorsement is a very popular method for advertising the products. Product popularity can be increased by linking it to someone who is already popular i.e. Celebrity. Celebrity Endorsement not only makes product familiar and popular but it also helps to break through the clutter. At this point one can easily state that anyone alive today, living in the western world, has encountered some form of celebrity endorsing. Celebrity endorsing has reportedly been around since the 1920’s, first using radio and later in the 1950’s using television as media tool. Hollywood movie stars were often used for commercials promoting products ranging from pies to cigarettes. Besides movie stars, sport stars were also used in commercials.

An Indian family used to read various newspapers and magazines which includes several advertisements for various products and thus a consumer is exposed to around 1000 ads per day. Moreover, people forget 80% of the information in just 24 hours. All these things lead to high amount of clutter. The situation is even worse for the low involvement product categories in which differentiation is very little. To defeat the clutter of all the brands one of the most prominent solution is 'Celebrity Endorsement' for the brand. This is because in low involvement categories consumers neither have the time nor the desire to comprehensively investigate and assess all the offerings available to them. As a result in such categories consumers often make purchase decisions on the basis of in store factors and extrinsic cues like endorsement of product by well-known person, innovative packaging etc.

Now a days a new trend in the arena of the celebrity endorsement has aroused and that is of using multiple celebrities for endorsing the same product only. There is very limited literature available which had evaluated impact of single vs. multiple celebrity for the same product.

Today, an Indian family used to read various newspapers and magazines per day. Moreover, each magazine and newspaper includes various advertisements for different products. So, and they are exposed to around 1000 ads per day. The media-explosion can thus be easily demonstrated.

Since, Print media is being considered as such a popular media in India through which one can reach large number of people at the same time, marketers usually tend to choose Print media for their advertisements so as to aware more number of people about their products simultaneously.

Hence taking into consideration the above things the present study is undertaken to evaluate the impact of Single Celebrity endorsement as well as Multiple Celebrity endorsement and especially for Print advertisements.

The Study involves mainly Low-involvement product. The reasons for using low-involvement product areas under.

Since low-Involvement Products are the products that have very little differentiation, advertisements play a very important role in influencing the buying behaviour/perception of consumers.

Low-involvement products are the products that consumers purchase it frequently and since low-involvement products are low-cost products, consumers' purchase decision do not involve any comprehensive process and consumer often make purchase decision on the basis of advertisements and in-store cues and extrinsic cues like endorsement of product by celebrity.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To determine the relative effectiveness of Single celebrity endorsed advertisements and multiple celebrity endorsed advertisements for low-involvement product on consumers' attitude towards advertisement.
- 2) To examine the comparative influence of Single celebrity endorsement with multiple celebrity endorsement on consumers' perception about Celebrity's credibility, sincerity, attractiveness, expertise and trustworthiness.
- 3) To analyse the comparative influence of Single celebrity endorsed advertisements and multiple celebrity endorsed advertisements for low-involvement product on consumers' purchase intention for the advertised product.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

John Mowen and Stephen brown³ (1981):- The researchers conducted the study mainly to evaluate the impact of single verses multiple celebrity endorsers. The study was done on large mid-western university at Oklahoma. The product considered for the study was pen. The researchers found from the study that when product is endorsed by multiple celebrities as compared to single celebrities then the believability about the advertisement and the endorsed product would be significantly high.

McCracken⁴ (1989):- McCracken, through his research give the definition of celebrity Endorser. According to him, a celebrity endorser is an individual who enjoys public recognition and who uses this recognition on behalf of a consumer good by appearing with it in an advertisement. His research shown that in general celebrity endorsement influences the feelings of the consumers and can also influence the attitude consumers have towards the advertisement and attitude towards the brands, which can increase the purchase intentions and, consequently, increase sales.

Ian Phau and Linda Lum⁵ (2000):- The study was done to investigate whether the physical attractiveness of endorser has any influence on consumer's purchase intention especially for print advertisements. For the purpose of the study, both high involvement product (Slimming

programme) & low involvement product (Skincare moisturizer) were selected. The results of the study shown that the impact of attractive endorser in influencing the views of audience was more powerful for high involvement products than for low involvement products.

Chung-kue Hsu and Daniella McDonald¹ (2002):- Celebrity Endorsement Advertising is a prevailing Advertising technique. Researchers through their research try to find out that which factors are responsible for making a multiple-celebrity endorsed advertising a successful one. The study was done on U.S.A. For the purpose of the study, milk mustache ads were used. It was found from the study that those ads where celebrity qualities like type, age, and gender, their intended audiences as well as milk attributes were in congruence/matching, were effective in influencing the target segment. Thus, the research shows that fit between the endorsed product and various celebrities is a key factor for using multiple celebrity endorsers in advertising.

Saleem⁷ (2007):- The study evaluated the perpetual difference of young adult toward single celebrity ads and multiple celebrities' ads. Questionnaires were administered on a sample of 300 university students to asses if there is any difference in young adult perception about single celebrity endorsement and multiple celebrities' endorsement. Four print media ads, two containing one celebrity in them and two containing three and five celebrities in them were used as a stimulus. The results showed that the attitude toward ad and purchase intentions are more positive for multiple celebrities ads compare to single celebrity ads and there is no significant difference in the attitude toward brand for multiple celebrities ads and single celebrity ads.

Pughazhendi, Antony Baskaran, Prakash and Balamurugan⁶ (2012):- The purpose of the study is to explore the perceptual difference of consumer towards single celebrity endorsement and multiple celebrity endorsement (more than one celebrity in a single advertisement) for high and low involvement products and services. Through the research, it was analysed that the attitudes toward advertisements, attitude toward brand and purchase intentions are more positive for multiple celebrities ad which belong to low involvement category while for high involvement product category attitude toward advertisements, attitude toward brand and purchase intention showed no significant difference for multiple and single celebrity advertisements.

Jayswal Rachita, Nirmal, and Panchal Priya² (2013):- The study aimed to analyze the impact of single verses multiple celebrity attractiveness and product match up on consumers' brand choice behaviour. Through their research, it was found that the advertisers while using single celebrity endorsement in their advertisements should consider both celebrity's attractiveness and celebrity-product congruence as an important factor in influencing consumers' brand choice behaviour. While, for multiple celebrity endorsement, it was found from the research that the celebrity's attractiveness was not significant factor in influencing consumers' brand choice behaviour.

4. DISTINGUISHING FEATURES OF THE STUDY

The previous studies undertaken have shown the relative effectiveness of advertisements endorsed by single Celebrity and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities on buying behaviour of consumers for different product categories (i.e. High involvement food products, high involvement non-food products, low involvement food products and low involvement non-food

products). While the present study shows the comparative analysis of impact of advertisements endorsed by Single Celebrity and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities on perception of consumers for low involvement product only.

The previous studies undertaken have evaluated the relative effectiveness of advertisements endorsed by single celebrity and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities for different products, while the present study shows the comparative analysis of impact of advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities on the perception of consumers for the same product.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **Target population:-** Adult consumers of Rajkot.
- **Place of Study:-** The study was undertaken in the month of June and July 2015 in the city of Rajkot, Gujarat, India.
- **Type of Research:-** Descriptive research. Since the aim of the study is to examine and analyze the perceptions, preferences and buying behaviour of consumers of Rajkot especially with respect to low involvement product category.
- **Research Hypothesis:-** The hypothesis tested using the study are:-
 - **H1:-** There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing consumer's attitude towards advertisement.
 - **H2:-** There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumer's purchase intention for the advertised product.
 - **H3:-** There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumers' perception about celebrity's credibility, sincerity, attractiveness, expertise and trustworthiness.
- **Sampling Plan**
 - **Samples and their size:-**
 - a) **Consumers:-** 200 adult consumers residing in Rajkot were considered for the study.
 - b) **Product Selected for Study:-** Low-involvement product(Soft drink) specifically Coca-cola was selected. Advertisement with single Celebrity and advertisement with multiple celebrities in it for Coca-cola were selected in order to know the perception of consumers.
 - **Sampling Method:-** Probability/Random sampling method was used for study.
- **Sources of Data:-** The research study employed both secondary and primary sources of data. The details are as under:-
 - **Primary sources of Data:-** Personal Interview and Mall Intercept.
 - **Secondary sources of Data:-** Rajkot related websites, Leading Magazines and Newspapers, Company Reports, Research papers, books.

6. EXPERIMENT/STUDY PROCEDURE

For conducting the study mainly Soft-drinks (i.e. low-involvement product) that consumers usually use to drink to get refreshed in day to day life was selected. The main reason for selecting such product was that such products are low cost products and consumers purchase it frequently, so consumers do not undergo comprehensive process in making their purchase decision and hence advertisements play very important role in affecting the purchase decision of consumers. Product selected for study was of very superior quality and was manufactured by the giant and leading company named COCA-COLA. Before the experiment took place, consumers consent was taken. Once consumers consent was obtained then they were interviewed individually. First, consumers were asked for their gender and age. Then the interviewer asked them what they did last weekend to make them feel more at ease. During the introduction, the interviewer emphasized that there were no right or wrong answers and that their own opinion was valued the most. A smiley board, depicting five faces that displayed increasing amounts of positive affect (1, deep frown: hate it; 5, big smile: love it), was used to help consumers respond to the questions. The consumer was asked two practice questions orally, which were designed to create diverse responses. Once it was apparent that the consumer understood the scale, then the experiment was conducted formally for both advertisements for the same product as follows.

7. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The study was undertaken in three phases. In 1st phase relative effectiveness of advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrities on consumer's attitude towards advertisement was analysed. In 2nd phase relative effectiveness of advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity, advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrities on consumer's purchase intention for the advertised product was analysed. In 3rd phase relative effectiveness of advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity, advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrities on consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, sincerity, trustworthiness, attractiveness and expertise was analysed.

DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Two created print advertisements are used as stimulus and thus they are considered as Independent variables. One advertisement for low involvement product named COCA-COLA consist of Single celebrity, and other advertisement for the same low involvement product named COCA-COLA consist of multiple celebrities).One dependent variable named Consumer Perception/buying behaviour was taken. To measure the perception of consumers, three variables were studied, Consumer's attitude towards advertisement, Consumer's purchase intention for the advertised product and Consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, expertise, trustworthiness, and honesty.

Two created Print advertisements are given below:

Print advertisement with single celebrity endorsement

Print advertisement with multiple celebrity endorsement

Figure 1: Print Advertisements of Soft Drink with Single celebrity and multiple celebrity endorsement for the same product COCA-COLA

Phase :1 Comparative Analysis of effectiveness of advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity for the product named COCA-COLA soft drink on Consumer's attitude towards advertisement especially in case of Print media.

- For carrying out the above analysis, a sample of 200 adult consumers was taken. The product considered for study was Soft Drink that consumers usually like to drink to get refreshed in his or her day to day life.
- Before starting the experiment, the age and gender was noted down. Consumer's attitude towards advertisement, a four-item scale, was measured on five point likert scale with five options on scale. Anchors used in this scale were: "attractive, appealing, convicting and credible". The subjects were asked to rate their opinion on five-point likert scale to measure the consumer's attitude towards advertisement.

After noting down the responses following hypothesis were developed and tested.

- **H_{null1}**: There is no significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity in influencing the consumer attitude towards advertisement for the same product especially in case of Print media.
- **H_{alt1}**: There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity in influencing the consumer attitude towards advertisement for the same product especially in case of Print media.

The responses of consumers were served as data for testing the above hypothesis. The resultant data was analyzed using the **Paired t-test (t-test for dependent samples)** using SPSS software. The value of alpha was assumed to be 0.05. The table that shows the output for the above hypothesis are given below.

Table 1: Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1	AdvertisementEndorsedBySingleCelebrity	1.9600	200	.98144	.06940
	AdvertisementEndorsedByMultipleCelebrity	3.0400	200	.93958	.06644

Table 2: Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	AdvertisementEndorsedBySingleCelebrity - AdvertisementEndorsedByMultipleCelebrity	-1.08000	1.23337	.08721	-1.25198	-.90802	-12.384	199	.000

From the table 2, it is observed that the two tail Sig. (Significance) value is .000 which is less than .05 which reveals that the **null hypothesis is rejected** (there is a significant difference between two conditions).

Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity in influencing the consumer’s attitude towards advertisement for the same product especially in case of Print media.

Also, the mean of second condition (advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrity) i.e. 3.04 is greater than the first condition (advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity) i.e. 1.96.

Hence the analysis showed that **Advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity has more favourable/positive impact as compared to advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity in creating more positive attitude towards advertisement.**

Phase :2 Comparative Analysis of effectiveness of advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity for the same product named COCA-COLA on Consumer’s purchase intention for the advertised product especially in case of Print media.

- For carrying out the above analysis, a sample of 200 adult consumers was taken. The product considered for study was Soft drink product that consumers usually like to drink to get refreshed in his or her day to day life.

- Before starting the experiment, the age and gender was noted down. Consumer purchase intention for the advertised product, a Six-item scale, was measured on five point likert scale with five options on scale. Anchors used in this scale were: “the coca-cola in the ad contains a lot of sugar (ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree on five-point likert scale), the Coca-cola in the ad is appropriate for the body (ranging from bad to good), the coca-cola in the ad is appropriate for the teeth(ranging from bad to good), the coca-cola in the ad influences health (ranging from unhealthy to healthy), the coca-cola in the ad has any influence on weight (ranging from negative to positive), and the coca-cola in the ad has any nutritional value (ranging from low to high)”. The subjects were asked to rate their opinion on five-point likert scale to measure the consumer’s purchase intention for the advertised product.

After noting down the responses following hypothesis were developed and tested.

- **H_{null1}**: There is no significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity in influencing the consumer purchase intention for the advertised product especially in case of Print media.
- **H_{alt1}** : There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrity in influencing the consumer purchase intention for the advertised product especially in case of Print media.

The responses of consumers were served as data for testing the above hypothesis. The resultant data was analyzed using the **Paired t-test** (t-test for dependent samples) using SPSS software. The value of alpha was assumed to be 0.05. The table that shows the output for the above hypothesis are given below.

Table 3: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 AdvertisementEndorsedbySingleCelebrity	2.4600	50	.95212	.13465
AdvertisementEndorsedbyMultipleCelebrity	3.5000	50	.97416	.13777

Table 4: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 AdvertisementEndorsedbySingleCelebrity - AdvertisementEndorsedbyMultipleCelebrity	-1.04000	1.49775	.21181	-1.46566	-.61434	-4.910	49	.000

From the table 4, it is observed that the two tail Sig. (Significance) value is .000 which is less than .05 which reveals that the **null hypothesis is rejected** (there is a significant difference between two conditions).

Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumer purchase intention for the Advertised product especially in case of Print media.

From the table 3, it is observed that the mean of second condition (advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrity) i.e. 3.5 is greater than the first condition (advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity) i.e. 2.46.

Hence, the analysis showed that **Advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities has more favourable/positive impact as compared to advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity in influencing the consumer purchase intention for the Advertised product.**

Phase :3 Comparative Analysis of effectiveness of advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities for Soft drink product named COCA-COLA on Consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, attractiveness, trustworthiness and expertise especially in case of Print media.

- For carrying out the above analysis, a sample of 200 adult consumers was taken. The product considered for study was Soft drink product that consumers usually like to drink to get refreshed in his or her day to day life.
- Before starting the experiment, the age and gender was noted down. Consumer's perception towards celebrity, a four-item scale, was measured on five point likert scale with five options on scale. Anchors used in this scale were: "Familiarity with celebrity (ranging from unfamiliar to very familiar), attractiveness of celebrity (ranging from unattractive to attractive), credibility of celebrity (ranging from uncredible to credible), and celebrity's look (ranging from ugly to beautiful)". The subjects were asked to rate their opinion on five-point likert scale to measure the consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, attractiveness, trustworthiness and expertise.

After noting down the responses following hypothesis were developed and tested.

- **H_{null1}** : There is no significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, expertise, attractiveness and trustworthiness especially in case of Print media.
- **H_{alt1}** : There is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumer's perception towards celebrity's credibility, expertise, attractiveness and trustworthiness especially in case of Print media.

The responses of consumers were served as data for testing the above hypothesis. The resultant data was analyzed using the **Paired t-test** (t-test for dependent samples) using SPSS software. The value of alpha was assumed to be 0.05. The table that shows the output for the above hypothesis are given below.

Table 5: Paired Samples Statistics

	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Pair 1 AdvertisementEndorsedBySingleCelebrity	3.2400	200	.81592	.05769
AdvertisementEndorsedByMultipleCelebrity	4.3600	200	.93529	.06614

Table 6: Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 AdvertisementEndorsedBySingleCelebrity - AdvertisementEndorsedByMultipleCelebrity	-1.12000	1.18007	.08344	-1.28455	-.95545	-13.422	199	.000

From the table 6, it is observed that the two tail Sig. (Significance) value is .000 which is less than .05 which reveals that the **null hypothesis is rejected** (there is a significant difference between two conditions).

Thus, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity, and advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities in influencing the consumer’s Perception towards celebrity’s credibility, expertise, trustworthiness and attractiveness especially in case of print media.

From the table 5, it is observed that the mean of second condition (advertisement endorsed by multiple celebrity) i.e. 4.36 is greater than the first condition (advertisement endorsed by Single celebrity) i.e. 3.24.

Hence, the analysis shows that the **Advertisements endorsed by multiple celebrities has more favourable/positive impact as compared to advertisements endorsed by Single celebrity in creating more positive Perception towards celebrity’s credibility, trustworthiness, expertise and attractiveness.**

8. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY & SCOPE OF FUTURE RESEARCH

- a) The study evaluated the impact of single verses multiple celebrity endorsement in the Print advertisement for one product only namely COCA-COLA soft drink. But the same impact could also be evaluated for other products like corn flakes, biscuits, wafers etc. Whose advertisements also incorporate Single and multiple celebrity endorsement in it.
- b) The select group of products, Celebrities and ages sampled limit the degree to which these findings can be generalized.
- c) The celebrities considered in the study especially for created Print advertisements were popular celebrities but it may happen that they may not be the favourite celebrities of consumer and hence this inconsistency may have affected the responses for products taste assessment and product liking.

Regardless of the above mentioned limitations the study is likely to be the first one in Indian and especially in Gujarat context to document the findings on impact of using single verses multiple celebrity in the advertisement for selling the low-involvement product COCA-COLA.

9. POLICY RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

- The study revealed that advertisements endorsed by more number of celebrities have significant impact in creating positive attitude towards advertisement. This information suggests that if advertisers of products make use of multiple celebrity endorsement for advertising their products then they are likely to get their desired impact and appropriate reach for the money spent.
- The study showed that the consumer's perception is more positive towards celebrity's credibility, expertise, trustworthiness and attractiveness as the number of celebrities in the ad increases. Thus, the marketers could make use of more number of celebrities in their advertisements for creating more positive perception of consumers towards celebrity's credibility, expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness and thereby selling their advertised products.
- The findings suggest that consumers get significantly influenced by multiple celebrities in the advertisement as compared to single celebrity endorsement for the same product. The findings also suggest that multiple celebrity endorsement is more influential for consumer's purchase intention for the advertised product. So one can make use of multiple celebrities in the advertisement for endorsing their products. The influence could be very high in case of low involvement soft-drink products such as Coca-cola that the consumers usually like to drink in his or her day to day life.

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